

variable range of seed set in the indica, indica/japonica, and japonica lines in crosses with indica pollinators may have been due to some genetically controlled incompatibility system, depending upon the degree of affinity between the parental varieties used in this study. Such a system has been reported to explain the intervarietal hybrid sterility in rice. $\mathcal{S}$

Diversification of cytoplasmic male sterility in rice

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Segregating lines of crosses between varieties of diverse origin were examined for male steriles occurring naturally.

In six of the seven male steriles isolated, sterility was found to be genetic. Cytological studies of these genetic male steriles showed regular meiosis, indicating pollen abortion in postmeiotic stages.

The other male sterile plant isolated from the F₂ of Ratna/Rajai had multiple pistils and whitish rudimentary anthers. This plant was propagated through stubbles and crosses were made. Spikelet fertility in the F₁s showed three classes of F₁ — completely sterile, partially fertile, and fertile — indicating that male sterility is conditioned by cytoplasmic-genetic factors.

Crosses were made with high yielding donors for resistance to disease and stress. In the F₁ hybrids, most varieties had varying fertility restoration ability. Maintainers of sterility were less common. Of the 40 hybrid combinations studied, only IET4699 and Surekha were identified as maintainers. Ratna, Kalinga III (CR237-1), and IET7302 were strong restorers. Utkal Prava (CR1030), Ta-poo-che-ze, and Rasi were weak maintainers.

Backcrosses with IET4699 and Surekha were made to transfer cytoplasmic sterility into their nuclear background. $\mathcal{S}$

Heritability of compact panicle and stigma color

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Heritability of compact and lax panicle was examined in the F₁ and F₂ of a cross of Dee-gee-woo-gen (lax) and BU-I (compact).

BU-I is a mutant isolated from X-ray irradiated NC1626. The compact panicles of this mutant have fewer secondary branches and shorter pedicel,

Table 1. Chi-square analysis of F₂ of Dee-gee-woo-gen/BU-I for compact panicle, West Bengal, India.

Panicle trait	Frequency	χ^2 ^a	Ratio
Lax	117	1.696	1:2:1
Intermediate	237		
Compact	102		

^ad.f. = 1 at 5% level = 3.841; at 1% level = 6.635.

Table 2. Analysis of F₂ of 4 crosses for stigma color, West Bengal, India.

Cross	Stigma color	Frequency	χ^2 ^a	Ratio
Dee-gee-woo-gen/BJ-I	Black	440	0.349	3:1
	White	155		
Dee-gee-woo-gen/BU-3	Black	232	0.068	3:1
	White	80		
IR8/CRM	Black	910	0.444	3:1
	White	290		
IR8/BU-3	Black	256	0.004	3:1
	White	84		
Pooled	Black	1633	0.325	3:1
	White	529		

^ad.f. = 2 at 5% level = 5.991.

resulting in closely attached spikelets. The primary branches also are closely attached with the main axis of the panicle.

The F₁ hybrids had intermediate panicles, resembling the female parent Dee-gee-woo-gen. The F₂ plants showed 3 distinct panicle types: compact (like BU-I); intermediate (like F₁); and lax (like Dee-gee-woo-gen), in a 1:2:1 ratio (Table 1). This indicates that this panicle character is controlled by a partially dominant gene.

To study stigma color, three strains (BJ-I, CRM6-5-90, BU-3) with black stigma and two strains (Dee-gee-woo-gen, IR8) with white stigma were crossed in these combinations: Dee-gee-woo-gen/BJ-I, Dee-gee-woo-gen/BU-3, IR8/CRM-6-5-90, and IR8/BU-3.

In the F₁, all hybrids had black stigma. F₂ plants had black and white stigma in a 3:1 ratio (Table 2). This indicates black stigma is controlled by a single dominant gene independent of apiculus color. $\mathcal{S}$

Root systems in hybrid rice

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Chinese scientists reported that strong and active root systems efficiently used applied fertilizers in hybrid rice. We

studied the root system of hybrid rice by the root pulling force method developed at IIRRI. The method assumes a correlation between the force required to pull seedlings or plants and strong, deep root systems which may confer drought tolerance. The results indicated that F₁ hybrids were significantly superior in root pulling force to their parents and check